

Cooperative learning (CL): “One of the most researched teaching methods in general and special education. CL in the National Curricula of Greece and the United Kingdom (UK), Comparative perspectives. Guidelines for the successful implementation of CL.”

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Abstract

This paper reports on collaborative learning as one of the most widely researched of all teaching methods in general and special education according to research. It discusses the benefits and difficulties of adopting this method in the Curricula in Greece and the United Kingdom (UK), and some comparative perspectives. The study of international literature was considered appropriate for the exploration of the topic. The ultimate aim is to provide greater opportunities for learning and socio-emotional development in terms of the following aspects: the benefits of implementing CL, the role of the teacher, the problems encountered and the purposes of CL. Through the research, it appeared that collaborative learning is one of the most valuable and fruitful areas of theory, research and practice in education. The purpose of this article, then, is to make it clear that cooperative learning exists when all students, both typical students and students with special educational needs, work together to achieve common learning goals (Johnson & Johnson, 1999). Each student can then achieve his or her learning goal if other group members achieve their (Johnson & Johnson, 1999).

Keywords: Collaborative learning (CL), students with special needs, National Curriculum (NC), comparative perspectives.

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1. Introduction

The cooperative movement was formed through the synthesis of many different theoretical schools. First and foremost, the Dewey school and the other representatives of the new education Kilpatrick (1871-1965) and Washbourne (1889-1968), held and applied cooperative teaching for two main reasons: the first, because of its potential to promote the socialization of the individual and the democratization of society and the second, cooperative learning was the only one that authentically ensures the condition of experimental learning (Matsaggouras, 2000) [1]. Secondly, it creates the need to avoid various social prejudices and similar attacks. The pioneer of this movement was Allport (1954/1979) and his followers who seek the smooth and creative integration of any kind of heterogeneous student population with the help of block-cooperative forms of organizing school life. In addition, the branch of social psychology that deals with group dynamics and studies the process of group formation, structures, the influence of group members and, finally, the behavior of the group towards other groups. A pioneer in this field was Lewin (1951) and modern representatives are Johnson and Johnson (1994), who tries to identify the mechanisms involved in the constructive settlement of past disagreements. Finally, another movement that supports collaborative learning is the psychology of cognitive development, and in particular that part of it which is bold epistemological reflection on the nature of knowledge and, of course, the conditions and processes of learning and development. The main representatives of this direction, which is known as (social) constructivism, are based on the work of Piaget and Vygotsky.

After more than 30 years of research including over several research studies on collaboration and learning, mere cooperation or mutual aid, while vital ingredients, are not enough to make collaborative learning effective. According to Baudrit (2007) [2], Gillies (2004) [3], Kanakis (2006) [4], there is a need for mutual aid to coexist with five other key elements: first, positive interdependence among group members, meaning that the success of each individual's goals depends on the success of others. However, to create positive interdependence, Johnson and Johnson (1975) [5] observed that it can be achieved in the following four ways: all team members strive to achieve a team goal and help

each other achieve it; the whole team receives recognition for achieving the goal; each team member has different resources that need to be combined to complete the specific goal; and each team member has a different role. Second, face-to-face interaction is vital because the level of team success depends significantly on the level and type of communication. Third, individual accountability that each person is responsible for their own learning, which contributes to the group's goal. As a result, teamwork is responsible for the process of each team member. Fourth, social skills are very important. Students with special disabilities do not know, for example, how to be leaders or communicate. So, they need to practice these skills in the group team. They are also evaluated by the team members. Fifth, group processing in which group members discuss how effectively they work with each other to achieve their goals, describe which members' actions are fruitful or not, and make decisions about which behaviors to continue or can be changed.

Collaborative learning is a well-documented and frequently recommended strategy for improving academic (Cohen & Lotan, 1997 [6]; Slavin, 1995a [7], 1995b [8]; Sharan, 1994 [9]), cognitive and social (Slavin, 1995b [8]) outcomes for all students, typical students and students with special educational needs. Cooperative learning methods attempt to reduce competition or individualism in classrooms by rewarding students based on the performance of all individuals in their group (Johnson & Johnson, 1981[10]; Slavin, 1983 [11]). It is important to note that teamwork is not itself collaborative learning, but that collaborative learning teams emphasize the academic learning success of each individual team member (Slavin, 1995a [7]). Essentially, collaborative learning methods explicitly use the power of the desegregated school - the presence of students of different races or ethnicities - to strengthen intergroup relations (Slavin, 1995b [8]).

There are thus several well-researched methods of cooperative learning.

- I. Group learning of students
- II. Student achievement teams (STAD): each team is like a microcosm of the whole class. Every week, the teacher introduces new material in a lecture or discussion.
- III. The game-tournament teams (TGT) have the same format as STAD. However, here

students play academic games to show their individual knowledge of the topic.

- IV. Team-based individualization (TAI) is a combination of group learning and individualized instruction applied to the teaching of mathematics.
- V. Jigsaw uses academic materials and students take individual quizzes covering all topics.
- VI. Learning together is a method where students work in heterogeneous groups of four to five members.
- VII. Group Investigation is a general classroom organization plan in which students work in small groups cooperatively.
- VIII. Other methods of cooperative learning (such as Wheeler, Peterson, Hamblin, Lew and Bryant, Weigel, Wiser and Cook)
- IX. In summary, each method is structured differently. For example, STAD, TGT and TAI are with well-defined group work and rewards, while Group Investigation and Learning Together give more freedom to students and less well-defined group rewards.

2. Collaborative learning in education: advantages and disadvantages

Mutual help, acceptance, encouragement, self-motivation of students, but also the spirits of individual responsibility for the common good are conducive to cooperative learning. What is very important for the success of this method is the role of the teacher. The teacher has to make certain decisions and be concerned about them, because the teacher as "primus inter pares" for his students is bound to certainly facilitate spontaneous and fruitful cooperation work (Petroulaki, 1981 op. cit. cited in Kanakis, 2006:156 [4]). Specifically, according to Anagnostopoulou (2001) [12], Baudrit (2007) [2], Gillies (2004) [3], Kossivaki (2006) [13], the teacher has the responsibility of multiple actions within the classroom. First of all, first action is to place the group in the classroom (square shape, T-shape, P-shape). Secondly, he has to organize the number of group members (corporate, three or four members). It would be preferable that the group team consists of two members. Due to the change from the traditional

method to other alternatives, there is a need to have a transition phase. In addition, the teacher can add an additional member to the group later and gradually add a fourth and fifth person, because the multi-member group is quite difficult to coordinate and requires more time. Thirdly, his role is to compose the team (mixed or not). It is beneficial to create a mixed group, consisting of people who differ in terms of educational abilities, hobbies, teaching style, gender and other areas related to learning and socialisation. Consequently, the group will be able to compensate for the disabilities of some students through the assistance of other members. On the other hand, good students feel more useful by helping their peers. In addition, the teacher should think about preference and sympathy among the group members. In general, cooperation between friends is easier because of the better and faster request of friends, but it always brings the desired result. In addition, the teacher must often change the members of the different groups, especially with regard to the more sympathetic and isolated students. However, in the beginning, it would be advisable that the group members be uniform in group performance. Fourth, it should synthesize the role of students in the group.

The principle here is for all students to assume all roles. Regarding the roles:

- *Manager/organiser*: can be a combination of a timekeeper - who ensures that the team completes the task on time; a task manager - who ensures that the team stays on task; material managers - who collects all the materials needed by the team and returns them safely; and a noise monitor - who keeps the team's noise within acceptable limits.
- *Recorder*: this person records the team's decisions and responses or ensures that larger writing tasks are completed correctly.
- *Reader*: the person who reads the material to the group
- *Controller*: who makes sure that everyone has mastered and understood the material
- *Academic assistant*: who helps students who are experiencing some weaknesses, encourages and praises the student.

Fifth, his/her role is related to the teacher's syllabus. It is achieved in three ways (Johnson, et

al., 2000 [14]). The first is the interdependence of the teaching material, such as the distribution of a questionnaire, the second is the interdependence of the information, each student is engaged in a different task, therefore the group presents a common task according to the material, and the last is the common evaluation and common rewards for all group members together.

In addition, the teacher is responsible for the logistics. All team members must be able to communicate and interact with other team members directly without making noise. Consequently, students must have enough space, free movement and easy access to the library. Finally, the teacher is the evaluator of the group work. The teacher should observe whether the groups are working and operating smoothly and correctly. Thus, the teacher's role is advisory, guiding, assisting and coordinating.

According to Johnson and Johnson (2009) [15], when teaching in groups, the role of teaching is divided into three main teaching profiles: the first profile is the ritualistic form of cooperative learning (Siciliano, 2001) [16]: the teacher's intervention is obvious and based on a predetermined lesson that boasts a medium-term goal. The second is the non-authoritarian form of cooperative learning: it involves choices and decisions of the teacher in order to provoke the students' self-activity, experience and inquiring disposition compared to the processing of the relevant subject. The application is recommended for the core subjects of the National Curriculum. Thus, the objective of group groups should be completed within one to two hours. The third one is the group lose-duration group: it involves choices and decisions made by the teacher in order to create bonds between friends.

However, according to Kanakis (2006) [4] and Kossivaki (2006) [13], Slavin (1985) the major problems that can be encountered when implementing collaborative learning in the classroom are the mode of discussion, unequal participation of group members, the way of asking questions, answering questions, emotional support of group members, exploiting group dynamics and completing the task. In particular, the huge learning heterogeneity and the different personalities of each child can create an additional difficulty in implementing cooperative learning (Cantwell and Andrews, 2002) [17]. For example, good students know how to help weak students, but they try to take the reins. This contributes to

the development of competition between students. Thus, the role of the teacher is so important in this particular condition. Moreover, the composition of the group according to the friends can lead to positive or negative results if the friends overstep the boundaries due to excessive cheerfulness. In addition to this problem, the teacher also faces practical problems such as oversized classrooms, non-existent or substandard libraries and fewer teaching aids, which are important factors that teachers do not implement cooperative learning. In addition, the National Curricula and the assessment of students exclusively by written exams produce an extremely rigid school (Chin-Tan et al., 2010) [18]. Thus, teachers' motivation should be reinforced by training seminars or enriched university curricula. In any case, collaborative learning and teaching is an alternative learning method that complements existing learning methods and does not replace them (Gillies, 2004 [3]`Johnson and Johnson, 2009 [15]`Kanakis, 2006 [4]).

Therefore, we all realize that it is difficult to achieve the goals of cooperative learning, which are to improve the academic skills of all team members, allowing them to face the world with more confidence, learn the skills of cooperation and respect for the opinion and beliefs of others, interact with others leading to the creation of a better intellectual activity, increase self-esteem, increase the ability of productive coordination and to produce what could be called "thinking interaction" so that all students, both typical students and students with special educational needs, are able to practice their developing cognitive and metacognitive skills (Johnson and Johnson, 2009) [15]. In addition, according to Kanakis (2006) [4] and Kossivaki (2006) [13] other valuable effects are: school discipline and positive behaviour in school, lower level of school anxiety, development of self-esteem and self-concept, improvement of students' speech quality and students' assessment is better when they can externalize their thoughts with words. (Iautes Denken). Each student speaks about more than in the traditional school method.

Continuing, society provides the school as a place of social reproduction. It must ensure that all students, both typical students and students with disabilities, have the necessary tools for future life, so that they can make the best progress in the areas of academic learning, cognitive development, social learning and emotional

development. Regarding the first area, collaboration maximizes learning because, first, this method enhances the students' interest in the subject matter; second, it notes different options of the problem; third, it gives the student the opportunity to clarify, relate, hypothesize, verify; and finally, it gives the student the opportunity to communicate the proposed solution to the problem. As far as the area of cognitive development is concerned, the organization of teaching according to cooperative learning creates the conditions that develop higher cognitive functions. Piaget considers cooperative experiences to be extremely important because critical thinking is more important than mere teaching and learning. The consequent confrontation of different views among students helps, as Piaget and Kohlberg pointed out, to free the individual from egocentric thinking and generally helps to accelerate cognitive and moral development (see Matsangouras 1982). Simply, confrontations and conflicts may threaten the cohesion of the group, then cohesion depends both on the behaviour of the teacher and on the cognitive-social abilities of the students. As regards the third area, cooperative learning contributes to the socialisation of the individual, which is one of the key factors in school education. It also reduces negative behaviour and creates better relationships between the teacher and the students as well as between classmates. Regarding the latter area, the group provides the most model behavior and the most opportunities in relationships. Finally, an additional domain, that of democratizing the individual, cooperation provides opportunities for equal participation in problem solving. (Gondovou-Mavrogiorgou-Papakonstantinou, 1985, 169) [19].

3. CL Curriculum in Greek SE

From the second half of the twentieth century and now into the twenty-first century, new curricula have changed dramatically. A recently introduced NC innovation common to all subjects is interdisciplinary teaching/learning (Alahiotis & Karatzia, 2006) [20]. The interdisciplinary approach is supported by active and experiential acquisition of knowledge, implemented through subject area teaching and interdisciplinary activities. A student-centred approach is promoted with peer and group learning that allows all students, both typical students and students with special educational needs, to develop initiatives,

become active and participate responsibly in the learning process (Fterniati & Spinthurakis, 2006) [21]. An example of how this innovation can be implemented is the implementation of the "flexible zone". The flexible zone is a defined period of time of detour within the school curriculum. Vygotsky constructed the term "flexible zone" focusing on the problem of understanding the child's developmental level and then organizing cognitive tasks or social demands of the environment in order to enhance the development of all children and children with special needs. In short, the interdisciplinary cooperation favoured by modern educational systems and the 'new school' is an ideal framework for experiential learning, the natural development of diverse skills and the development of team spirit and socialisation of people with disabilities (see Matsangouras, 2000 [1]; YPDMTH 2010: 24 and 25 [22]; YPDMTH 2011: 13 [23]).

However, the inability to adopt alternative methods of learning is evident, which can be highlighted by the aims and objectives of the National Curricula. This means that the teacher is attached to the National Curriculum, using monologues. Consequently, the gap between 'good' and 'bad' pupils or 'typical pupils' and 'disabled pupils' is widening all the time. The gap is also widened by the socio-economic differences of students in families. Thus, the National Curriculum ignores multiculturalism as a dominant element of Greek society. Moreover, it is clear that the direct linking of content and learning methods with the unilateral assessment of students in the context of written examinations is not a good way of testing, because this is the only way of testing that does not promote the purpose and goal of the school.

In conclusion, after several attempts by the teacher to introduce group work into the classroom, group work can create an environment that provides greater opportunities for learning and social-emotional development. Nevertheless, the transition from traditional teacher-centred teaching to group teaching is documented as a complex process, complicated and sometimes painful, as it changes the way teachers and students are used to acting and functioning. This requires planning, careful steps, time and support (Bagakis et al., 2008) [24]. Together they create a framework of authentic and more effective practice that can lead to students becoming active

and critical citizens in the 21st century (Fterniati & Spinthurakis, 2006) [21].

4. CL SE Curriculum in the UK

It is widely accepted that collaborative learning has several advantages. Given that they are well known, it is surprising that the actual practice of collaborative learning is still uncommon. Communication and interaction between learners in the group is rare, but a few years later (Galton and Williamson, 1992) [25] some steps towards change were found (Galton and Williamson, 1992) [25]. However, more recently there has been a progressive change. One such example is SPRinG' (Social Pedagogic Research into Grouping), (Blatchford, et al 2003) [26] in the UK has shown positive benefits for student learning, motivation and relationships. Thus, collaborative learning is becoming increasingly widespread.

In English schools teachers have a belief in addressing the individual needs of pupils. This lack of teamwork and individual focus is imposed by the school curriculum and classroom environment. Teachers believe that 'group work is no good' and so they do not develop other pedagogical methods. However, the results of the SPRinG project show that group work has positive effects on children's progress: more active and greater connection within the group. For this reason, teachers should use group work as a way of learning in the classroom and in their curriculum. The SPRinG study provides a number of useful insights into the ways in which teachers can incorporate effective teamwork in the classroom.

In general, there is now an increasing use of collaborative learning across the curriculum, from pair work to group work to embedded use (Jolliffe.). The level of commitment of the head teacher and senior management in schools contributes to this. The school not only ensures that all new members of staff are trained in collaborative learning, but ensures that all staff training, regardless of focus, is done through the use of collaborative learning methods. In other words, the school has become a collaborative learning community.

5. Comparative perspectives

In the context of the Lisbon strategy, European cooperation in education and training is at the heart of the programme and a key element in pursuing the 2020 perspective. The creation of an education-research-innovation 'knowledge triangle' that works well and helps all citizens to acquire better skills is fundamental to growth. The Strategic Framework for European Union (EU) cooperation in education and training identifies four long-term strategic objectives (Strategic Framework for EU cooperation in E&T, 2008) [27]. First, the first is to make lifelong learning and mobility a reality. The second is to improve the quality and effectiveness of education and training. The third is to promote equality, social cohesion and active citizenship. Finally, the fourth condition is to enhance creativity and innovation, including entrepreneurship, at all levels of education and training.

Therefore, teachers need to have the full range of subject knowledge, subject knowledge, altitude and pedagogical skills to help all students, typical students and students with special needs. In particular, according to the European Commission (2007) [28], they need altimeters to recognise the needs of every student, including those with specific disabilities, and respond to them by applying a wide range of teaching methods; to support student development; to help students to have basic altitudes; to work in multicultural environments, understanding the value of diversity and showing respect; and to work with colleagues, parents and the wider community.

In addition, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD's) Teaching and Learning International Survey (TALIS) is the first international survey to focus on teachers' working conditions and the learning environment in schools. It aims to help countries review and develop policies that are conducive to conditions conducive to effective schooling (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, 2009) [29]. The concept of professional learning communities has its roots in the ideas of socio-constructivism. Central features are collaboration, a focus on learning, reflective inquiry and the de-privatisation of practice. In addition, according to the literature, small school size, high autonomy and school leadership that feels responsible for improving teaching, and a culture of constructive feedback can improve a professional learning community. Thus, this data from International Survey on Teaching and Learning (TALIS) on

profiles related to these practices can contribute to an implementation audit (Teaching Practices and Pedagogical Innovations: Evidence from TALIS, 2012) [30].

From comparative and international education, we also see some challenges for the future. First of all, to continue to explore "what works", to maintain a critical commentary on educational policy decisions, to promote positive developments in the ethics of cooperation and research with the "other", to continue to monitor the work of international organizations, and to develop methods of comparative research (Phillips & Schweisfurth, 2007) [31].

In summary, international educational research places great emphasis on interdisciplinary curricula and interdisciplinary schooling in order to provide meaningful literacy for all students and students with diverse needs to meet the evolving demands of the times. There are some difficulties in implementing these curricula, but the sustainability of innovative programmes will be a function of how the education system should respond to and support the implementation of such a disruptive and different curriculum.

6. Guidelines for effective CL in the educational process

Ornstein argues that there are some important strategies as guidelines for collaborative learning, which have been developed by David and Roger Johnson in various texts. Some of these strategies are presented below:

- Organise the classroom to promote cooperative goals;
- Present the objectives as group objectives;
- Communicate intentions and expectations;
- Encourage a division of labour where appropriate;
- Encourage students to share ideas, materials, and resources;
- Supply a variety of materials;
- Encourage students to communicate their ideas clearly;
- Encourage supportive behaviour and point out rejecting or hostile behavior;
- Provide appropriate cues and signals;

- Monitor the group;
- Evaluate the individual and group;
- Reward the group for successful completion of its task.

In a complementary review, any cooperative learning course should include five key elements: (1) positive interdependence, (2) face-to-face interaction, (3) individual accountability, (4) social skills, and (5) group processing. (Ornstein, 1990: 425-426) [32].

7. Conclusions

Collaborative learning is a different and innovative event in the history of educational research. This method was based on well-established social psychological theory, constructed to meet classroom needs, evaluated in various methodological field experiments, and eventually widely disseminated (Slavin, 1992) [33]. Nowadays, cooperative learning has been shown in a large number and wide variety of studies to positively affect and improve students' self-esteem or internal control or race relations and various other outcomes.

On the threshold of the 21st century, the educational community around the world has succeeded in integrating collaborative learning into the educational process. Collaborative learning is one of the most alternative educational methods, which are being claimed as a result of contemporary currents in teaching pedagogy (Matsangouras, 2000) [1]. Cooperative learning or cooperative group teaching involves students working together in small learning groups, helping each other to perform individual and group tasks (Mitchell, 2008) [34]. In short, this strategy helps students learn from each other. In particular, collaborative group learning benefits all students, both typical students and students with disabilities, to progress to higher levels of learning and higher stages of development and socialization (Duque et al., 2020) [35].

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